

TORSIONAL PROPERTIES OF A STIFFENED COMPOSITE TUBE

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ABSTRACT

To reduce the structural weight, thin-walled circular composite tube has been used as a main spar of high altitude-long endurance unmanned air vehicle (HALE UAV). Predicting the torsional response of stiffened circular spar is complex due to the inhomogeneous nature of section properties, which are dependent on fibre architecture and constituent material properties. The stiffeners were placed in the top and bottom sectors of a tube to increase the torsional capabilities such as the rigidity and buckling strength. Numerical simulations were performed to estimate the effect of the stiffener on the torsional capacities. A static experimental test was performed on a stiffened tube, and the test results were compared with a numerical model. The numerical models showed good correlation and demonstrated the ability to predict the torsional capacity. Results presented herein will exhibit the effectiveness of stiffener on torsional strength and stiffness.

1 INTRODUCTION

Recently, composite materials have been widely used in aircraft design such as a solar powered high-altitude long endurance unmanned air vehicle (HALE-UAV) [1~2]. In this study, a tubular composite tube was applied to the main spar of a HALE-UAV wing. Fig. 1 shows the cross-section of the wing. Fig. 2 shows the prototype of a typical wing-section. A circular tube is widely used as a spar in light weight UAV wings, because a cylindrical tube has both high bending and torsional rigidity [3].

Figure 1: Wing cross-section

Figure 2: Prototype of typical wing-section

The spar cap is positioned on upper and lower section to increase the torsional strength and rigidity of circular spar. Fig. 3 shows a schematic diagram of a circular spar with cap. This study focuses on the structural response of stiffened circular spar under torsional loading. Torsion tests were conducted to estimate the effects of the cap on buckling strength and rigidity. And computational simulations were performed to study the effect of spar caps.

Figure 3: Schematic diagram of a circular spar with cap

2 TORSION TESTS

Torsional load was applied until failure and torque and rotation angle were measured by a torque sensor and angle sensor. Torsional rigidity was calculated from torque angle curve using following equation.

$$GJ = \frac{TL}{\theta} \quad (1)$$

Where T is the torque, L is the span length and θ is the angle in radians. Figure 4 shows the test setup.

Figure 4: Setup in torsion test

A circular spar was cured in an autoclaved in a single cure cycle. The circular spars were fabricated using H3055 CFRP prepreps. The dimensions and layup of spar shown in Table 1 and Figure 5. The length of spar is 0.6 m. And Figure 6 shows the fabricated test specimens. Figs. 7-11 are the test results of Table 1. These figures show that the effects of cap on collapse load. The cap increases the torsional strength.

Table 1: Summary of layup pattern of a spar

Case	Dia (mm)	Base Layup	Cap Layup	Type
M30-1	30.0	[0/90/0]	-	-
M30-2	30.0	[0/90/0]	[0 ₂]	Sym.
M30-3	30.0	[0/90/0]	[0 ₂]	Unsym.
M30-4	30.0	[0/90/0]	[0 ₄]	Sym.
M30-5	30.0	[0/90/0]	[0 ₄]	Unsym.

Figure 5: Setup in torsion test

Figure 6: Test specimens

Figure 7: Torsional response for M30-1

Figure 8: Torsional response for M30-2

Figure 9: Torsional response for M30-3

Figure 10: Torsional response for M30-4

Figure 11: Torsional response for M30-5

3 FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

The commercial finite element software NASTRAN was used for computational analysis of stiffened circular spar. The torsional buckling strength and rigidity were computed and compared with test data. The mechanical properties of a lamina are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Material properties of H3055 CFRP lamina

Properties	Values
E_1 (GPa)	146.1
E_2 (GPa)	7.7
G_{12} (GPa)	3.6
ν_{12}	0.355
σ_{1t} (MPa)	2551.8
σ_{1c} (MPa)	945.2
σ_{2t} (MPa)	36.7
σ_{2c} (MPa)	156.1
Thickness (mm)	0.094

Fig. 12 shows the buckling modes of FEM analysis and test. And comparison of buckling strength between tests and numerical results shown in Table 3.

(a) FEM analysis

(b) Test

Fig. 12 Buckling mode of tubular spar

Table 3: Comparison of torsional buckling strength between tests and numerical results

Case	Test (N-m)	Numerical (N-m)	Numerical / Test
M30-1	8.93	8.59	0.96
M30-2	12.64	13.48	1.07
M30-3	10.27	10.00	0.97
M30-4	15.76	17.54	1.11
M30-5	9.85	10.64	1.08

The torsional rigidity for stiffened spar is given by following equation. The unit torsion load is applied and rotation angles are extracted from the FEM model.

$$GJ = \frac{1}{\phi_{i+1} - \phi_i} \int_i^{i+1} T ds \quad (2)$$

Where ϕ is the rotation angle of section and T is the torsional moment. Fig. 13 shows the finite element model for torsional rigidity analysis. The comparison of torsional rigidity between tests and numerical results shown in Table 4.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, numerical simulation and test have been performed to investigate the torsional strength and rigidity of a stiffened circular cylindrical spar. The numerical model was compared with the test.

The numerical model shows good agreement with the test results. The spar caps were placed in the top and bottom sector of a spar to increase the torsional capabilities such as the rigidity and collapse load. The results show that the stiffened circular spar can be used effectively for light weight UAV structure.

Fig. 13 FEM model for torsional rigidity analysis

Table 4: Comparison of torsional rigidity between tests and numerical results

Case	Test (N-m)	Numerical (N-m)	Numerical / Test
M30-1	21.39	24.22	0.88
M30-2	26.76	26.79	1.0
M30-3	23.77	24.29	0.98
M30-4	30.05	27.34	1.10
M30-5	24.97	27.91	0.89

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